

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Annex 3.3 to AD4.1 – General Survey Questionnaire for Adults (18 – 39 years)

WP 4

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¹ PU = Public

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Document history

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Version 2	2023-07-11	Hardiesse Bessonneau /SpF/ Hardiesse.BESSONNEAU@santepubliquefrance.fr; Liese Gilles /VITO/ liese.gilles@vito.be	Small adaptations after external review of AD4.1
Version 3	2023-09-18	Liese Gilles /VITO/ liese.gilles@vito.be	Small adaptations after GS partners' review of the questionnaires

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I.00: Questionnaire information

- Q093: Id (participant) _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
Q094: Id (interviewer) _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q095: Date of the interview (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q095.1: Day _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q095.2: Month _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q095.3: Year _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
Q098: Interview place / interview platform _____ (Priority.OPTIONAL)

I.01: Personal information

- Q001: What sex were you assigned at birth?
 Male
 Female
 Intersexual
(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
Q002: What is your birth date? (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q002.1: Year _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q002.2: Month _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q002.3: Day _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
Q099: How do you identify yourself with respect to gender?
 Male
 Female
 Transgender
 Non-binary
 Other
 I don't want to put myself in a gender
(Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 Q099.1: Specify other _____ (Priority.OPTIONAL)

I.02: Sociodemographic information

- Q003: In which country were you born? _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
Q004: How long have you been living ...? Please indicate the number of years (or months if less than 1 year) and the details of your current address. (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q004.1: In this country (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q004.1.1: Years _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q004.1.2: Months _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q004.2: In your current address (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q004.2.1: Years _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q004.2.1: Months _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q004.3: Current address details (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q004.3.1: Street name and number _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q004.3.2: Postal code _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

Q005: What is the highest level of education you and your partner (if applicable) attained?

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.1: You **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q005.1.1: Level

- No formal education or below primary education (iscd 0)
- Primary education (iscd 1)
- Lower secondary education, or second stage of basic education (iscd 2)
- Upper secondary education (iscd 3)
- Post-secondary non-tertiary education (iscd 4)
- Short-cycle tertiary education (iscd 5)
- Bachelor's or equivalent level (iscd 6)
- Master's or equivalent level (iscd 7)
- Doctoral or equivalent level (iscd 8)
- Other
- Not applicable

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.1.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q005.2: Your partner (if applicable) **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q005.2.1: Level

- No formal education or below primary education (iscd 0)
- Primary education (iscd 1)
- Lower secondary education, or second stage of basic education (iscd 2)
- Upper secondary education (iscd 3)
- Post-secondary non-tertiary education (iscd 4)
- Short-cycle tertiary education (iscd 5)
- Bachelor's or equivalent level (iscd 6)
- Master's or equivalent level (iscd 7)
- Doctoral or equivalent level (iscd 8)
- Other
- Not applicable

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.2.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q007: What ethnic origin do you have? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q007.1: Origin

- Caucasian
- Arab (including north africa and the middle east)
- Sub-saharan african
- Latin-american
- South asian (including pakistan)
- Far east asia (including china and the philippines)
- Mixed/multiracial
- Other
- Do not know
- Do not wish to answer

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q007.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q008: Which language(s) is (are) spoken at home? **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q008.1: National language(s) [country of study]

- Yes
- No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

Q008.2: Another language

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q008.3: Specify language(s) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q100: Were your biological parents born in the same country as you? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q100.1: Mother

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q100.1.1: Please specify if in another country _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q100.2: Father

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q100.2.1: Please specify if in another country _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q101: What is your current main labour status and your partner's main labour status (if applicable)?

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q101.1: You

Employee working full-time

Employee working part-time

Self-employed working full-time (including family worker)

Self-employed working part-time (including family worker)

Unemployed

Pupil, student, further training, unpaid work experience

In retirement or in early retirement or has given up business

Permanently disabled or/and unfit to work

In compulsory military community or service

Fulfilling domestic tasks and care responsibilities

Other inactive person

Other status

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q101.1.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q101.2: Your partner (if applicable)

Employee working full-time

Employee working part-time

Self-employed working full-time (including family worker)

Self-employed working part-time (including family worker)

Unemployed

Pupil, student, further training, unpaid work experience

In retirement or in early retirement or has given up business

Permanently disabled or/and unfit to work

In compulsory military community or service

Fulfilling domestic tasks and care responsibilities

Other inactive person

Other status

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q101.2.1: Specify other _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

I.03: Dietary habits

Q009: How often did you consume the following food categories in the last 12 months? Choose from the following options: **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q009.1: Fish and seafood

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.2: Meat

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.3: Dairy products

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.5: Cereals

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.6: Fats (eg. Oil, butter, ...)

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.7: Vegetables

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.8: Fruits

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.9: Snacks (e.G. Potato chips, bars, crackers...)

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.10: Nuts

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.12: Drinks with caffeine (e.G. Coffee, soft drinks, energetic drinks)

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010: How often did you consume the following seafood and fish species items in the last 3 months? Choose from the following options: **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.1: White fish (e.G. Hake, snapper, sea bream, cod, haddock, grouper, halibut, tilapia, bass)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.1.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3/ week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.1.2: Portion

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.2: Small oily fish (e.G. Anchovy, sardines, salmon) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.2.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3/ week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.2.2: Portion

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.3: Big oily fish (e.G. Sword fish, tuna, school shark) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.3.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3/ week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.3.2: Portion

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.4: Other sea food (e.G. Octopus, squid, shrimps, scampi) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.4.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3/ week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.4.2: Portion

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.6: Sea bass - aquacultured **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.6.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3/ week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.6.2: Portion

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.7: Sea bass **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.7.1: Frequency

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3/ week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.7.2: Portion

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.8: Swordfish **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.8.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3/ week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.8.2: Portion

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.9: Seabream **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.9.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3/ week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.9.2: Portion

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.10: Tuna (excluding canned tuna) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.10.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3/ week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.10.2: Portion

- A

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.11: Tuna - canned **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.11.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3/ week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.11.2: Portion

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.12: Mackerel (excluding canned mackerel) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.12.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3/ week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.12.2: Portion

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.13: Mackerel - canned **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.13.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3/ week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.13.2: Portion

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.14: Monkfish **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.14.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3/ week

4-6 / week

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.14.2: Portion

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.15: Perch **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.15.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3/ week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.15.2: Portion

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.16: Pike **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.16.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3/ week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.16.2: Portion

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.17: Other fish **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.17.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.17.2: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3/ week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.17.3: Portion

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

Q010.18: Other fish **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.18.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.18.2: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3/ week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.18.3: Portion

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.19: Other fish **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.19.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.19.2: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3/ week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.19.3: Portion

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q011: Did you eat fish or other seafood items in the last 14 days?

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012: How often did you consume the following food items in the last 12 months? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.1: Eggs **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.1.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.1.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.2: Cabbages **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.2.1: Frequency

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.2.2: Portion sizes

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.3: Cucurbitaceae (cucumber, pumpkins, zucchini) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.3.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.3.2: Portion sizes

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.4: Beans, peas and lentils **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.4.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.4.2: Portion sizes

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.5: Orchard fruits (apples, pears, plums, figs…) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.5.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.5.2: Portion sizes

- A

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.6: Strawberries **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.6.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.6.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.7: Other berries (grapes, blueberries...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.7.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.7.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.8: Dried fruits **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.8.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.8.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.9: Ready meals (in plastic packaging) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.9.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.10: Fast food **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.10.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.11: Rice **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.11.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.11.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.12: Other cereals (barley, oats, bran, wheat, rye, maize) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.12.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.12.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.13: Mushrooms **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.13.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.13.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.14: Potatoes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.14.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.14.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.15: Leafy vegetables (e.G. Spinach, romaine lettuce, kale, swiss shard, endives, collard greens···)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.15.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.15.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.16: Wild game meat **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.16.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.16.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.17: Offal **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.17.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.17.2: Portion sizes

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.18: Processed meat (ham, sausage, bacon, deli meats (such as bologna, smoked turkey and salami), hot dogs, jerky, pepperoni) **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q012.18.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q012.18.2: Portion sizes

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q012.19: Meat substitutes (eg: tofu) **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q012.19.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q012.19.2: Portion sizes

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q013: In the past 12 months, how often were the eggs that you ate from your own hens or received/bought from neighbours, friends, family or local growers?

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q015: How do you usually eat vegetables and fruits? **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q015.1: Vegetables

- Without skin
- With skin

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Both with skin and without skin

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q015.2: Fruits

Without skin

With skin

Both with skin and without skin

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017: Did you consume organic food in the last 12 months?

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q017.1: How often did you usually consume organic food in the last 12 months?

<1 / month

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q017.2: Which percentage of your diet is based on organic food? Indicate a percentage for each of the following food items (0%= nothing organic and 100%= all the food consumed is organic) Choose from the following options: **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q017.2.1: Vegetables

0% (never)

Less than 25% of the time

25% - 50% of the time

50% - 75% of the time

More than 75% of the time

100% (always)

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.2: Fruits

0% (never)

Less than 25% of the time

25% - 50% of the time

50% - 75% of the time

More than 75% of the time

100% (always)

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.3: Bread

0% (never)

Less than 25% of the time

25% - 50% of the time

50% - 75% of the time

More than 75% of the time

100% (always)

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.4: Meat

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- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.5: Eggs

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.6: Dairy products

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.7: Rice, pasta and other cereals

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.8: Other foods

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.8.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q018: Did you eat vegetables and/or fruit from your own garden or received/bought from neighbours, friends, family or local growers in the last 12 months? If yes, indicate per season the portion you have eaten locally-grown products (0%= nothing and 100%= all fruit/vegetables is from local sources) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q018.1: Fruits **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q018.1.1: Winter

- 0% (never)

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- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q018.1.2: Spring

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q018.1.3: Summer

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q018.1.4: Autumn

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q018.2: Vegetables **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q018.2.1: Winter

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q018.2.2: Spring

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q018.2.3: Summer

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q018.2.4: Autumn

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q019A: How much water do you drink on average each day? (do also think of water in hot beverages and soups!)

- Less than 1 l/day
- 1-2 l/day
- 2-3 l/day
- 3-5 l/day
- More than 5 l/day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q020: What is the main source of your water? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q020.1: Water for drinking

- Public network
- Bottled water (plastic)
- Bottled water (glass)
- Private well
- Others
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q020.1.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q020.2: Water for cooking

- Public network
- Bottled water (plastic)
- Bottled water (glass)
- Private well
- Others
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q020.2.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q021: Do you use water purification devices or water filtering systems for your water? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q021.1: Water for drinking

- Filter (faucet attachment, refrigerator filter)
- Water softener

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- Other
- No treatment
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q021.1.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q021.2: Water for cooking

- Filter (faucet attachment, refrigerator filter)
- Water softener
- Other
- No treatment
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q021.2.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q022: in which of the following bottling types do you usually consume beverages? Please consider all beverages (fruit juices, ice tea, soft drinks...) including water (multiple answers possible) Choose from the following options:

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q022.1: Beverages in glass bottling

- Yes
- No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q022.2: Beverages in plastic bottling

- Yes
- No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q022.3: Beverages from decorated colored glass

- Yes
- No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q022.4: Canned beverages

- Yes
- No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q022.5: Drinks prepared in metal recipients (e.G. Arabic teapot)

- Yes
- No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q022.6: Other types

- Yes
- No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q022.6.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q022.7: Don't know

- Yes
- No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q023: Do you use the following containers for keeping the food in the refrigerators or for longer-time storage elsewhere? If yes, how often do you use it? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q023.1: Hard plastic containers

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2 – 3/ month

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- 1 – 3/ week
- 4 – 6/ week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.2: Soft plastic container

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2 – 3/ month
- 1 – 3/ week
- 4 – 6/ week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.3: Baking paper

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2 – 3/ month
- 1 – 3/ week
- 4 – 6/ week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.4: Plastic bag

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2 – 3/ month
- 1 – 3/ week
- 4 – 6/ week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.5: Aluminium containers

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2 – 3/ month
- 1 – 3/ week
- 4 – 6/ week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.6: Ceramic containers

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2 – 3/ month
- 1 – 3/ week
- 4 – 6/ week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.7: Glass containers

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- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2 – 3/ month
- 1 – 3/ week
- 4 – 6/ week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.8: Others

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2 – 3/ month
- 1 – 3/ week
- 4 – 6/ week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.8.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q024: Do you use the following containers for preparing or heating your food in the microwave oven? If yes, how often do you use it? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q024.1: Hard plastic containers

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2 – 3/ month
- 1 – 3/ week
- 4 – 6/ week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q024.2: Soft plastic containers

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2 – 3/ month
- 1 – 3/ week
- 4 – 6/ week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q024.3: Ceramic containers

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2 – 3/ month
- 1 – 3/ week
- 4 – 6/ week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q024.4: Others

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2 – 3/ month

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

- 1 – 3/ week
- 4 – 6/ week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q024.4.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q025: What materials do you use as cookware for cooking and frying (e.G. Pots, pans, fryer, robots, making bread machine etc.) Choose from the following options: **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q025.1: Steel

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2-3 / month
- 1 / week
- 2-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q025.2: Ceramic

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2-3 / month
- 1 / week
- 2-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q025.3: Glass

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2-3 / month
- 1 / week
- 2-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q025.4: Teflon baking tray/covered pan

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2-3 / month
- 1 / week
- 2-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q025.5: Others

- Yes
- No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q025.5.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2-3 / month
- 1 / week
- 2-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q025.5.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q025.6: Don't know **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026: Do you consume dietary supplements (e.G. Vitamins and minerals)

Checked

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.4: Vitamin d

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.6: Iron

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.7: Zinc

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.8: Selenium

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.10: Fish oil

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.11: Folic acid

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.12: Algae or seaweed supplement

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.13: Multivitamins supplement

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.14: Multiminerals supplement

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.16: Other supplements

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q027: How often do you eat dishes from communal catering, such as from a canteen, dining hall or cafeteria in the last 4 weeks?

- (nearly) never
- 2 – 3/ month
- 1 – 3/ week
- 4 – 6/ week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day

7 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

I.04: Lifestyle

Q028: In relation to smoking habits, which of the following options best describe your situation? Please, specify all the information for the situation chosen. Choose from the following options: **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1: Have you ever smoked?

- Yes
- No

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q028.1.1: I was a smoker but i gave up smoking

- Yes
- No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.1.1: Age start smoking **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.1.1: Years _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.1.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.2: Age stop smoking **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.2.1: Years _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.2.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3: Type/variety and average of consumption **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.1: Cigarettes [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.1.1: No. Per day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.1.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.2: Pipes [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

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Q028.1.1.3.2.1: No. Per day _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.1.3.2.2: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.1.3.3: Cigars [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.1.3.3.1: No. Per day _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.1.3.3.2: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.1.3.4: Electronic cigarettes [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.1.3.4.1: Times used per day

[] Once

[] 2-5 times

[] 6-10 times

[] More than 10 times

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.1.3.4.2: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.1.3.5: Hookah [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.1.3.5.1: No. Per day _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.1.3.5.2: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.1.3.6: Products for smoking cessation [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.1.3.6.1: No. Per day _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.1.3.6.2: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.1.3.7: Others [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.1.3.7.1: No. Per day _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.1.3.7.2: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.1.3.7.3: Specify other _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.2: I currently smoke

[] Yes

[] No

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q028.1.2.1: Age start smoking (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.2.1.1: Years _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.2.1.2: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.2.2: Type/variety and average of consumption (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.2.2.1: Cigarettes [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.2.2.1.1: No. Per day _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.2.2.1.2: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.2.2.2: Pipes [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.2.2.2.1: No. Per day _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.2.2.2.2: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.2.2.3: Cigars [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.2.2.3.1: No. Per day _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.2.2.3.2: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.2.2.4: Electronic cigarettes [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.2.2.4.1: Times used per day

[] Once

[] 2-5 times

[] 6-10 times

[] More than 10 times

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.2.2.4.2: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.2.2.5: Hookah [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.2.2.5.1: No. Per day _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.2.2.5.2: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

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Q028.1.2.2.6: Products for smoking cessation [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.6.1: No. Per day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.6.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.7: Others [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.7.1: No. Per day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.7.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.7.3: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3: I use smokeless tobacco products (e.G., snuff, dipp, chewing tobacco)

[] Yes

[] No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.3.1: Age start **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.1.1: Years _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.1.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.2: Type/variety and average of consumption **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.2.1: Snuff [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.2.1.1: No. Per day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.2.1.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.2.2: Dip [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.2.2.1: No. Per day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.2.2.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.2.3: Chewing tobacco [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.2.3.1: No. Per day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.2.3.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029: How many people living in your house smoke or vape regularly (indoors)? Please provide a number _____

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1: For each of them, please indicate the average number of cigarettes smoked and the average times of e-cigarettes used per day indoors **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.1: Member no.1 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.1.1: Cigarettes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.1.1.1: No. /day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.1.1.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.1.2: Electronic cigarettes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.1.2.1: Times /day

[] Once

[] 2-5 times

[] 6-10 times

[] More than 10 times

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.1.2.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.2: Member no.2 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.2.1: Cigarettes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.2.1.1: No. /day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.2.1.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.2.2: Electronic cigarettes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.2.2.1: Times /day

[] Once

[] 2-5 times

[] 6-10 times

[] More than 10 times

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

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Q029.1.2.2.2: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.3: Member no.3 (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.3.1: Cigarettes (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.3.1.1: No. /day _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.3.1.2: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.3.2: Electronic cigarettes (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.3.2.1: Times /day

[] Once

[] 2-5 times

[] 6-10 times

[] More than 10 times

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.3.2.2: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.4: Member no.4 (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.4.1: Cigarettes (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.4.1.1: No. /day _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.4.1.2: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.4.2: Electronic cigarettes (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.4.2.1: Times /day

[] Once

[] 2-5 times

[] 6-10 times

[] More than 10 times

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.4.2.2: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q030: In general, how long, on a daily average, did you usually spend in the following indoor places where people smoke? (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q030.1: At home

[] Never

[] <1h/day

[] 1-4h/day

[] >4h/day

[] Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q030.2: Elsewhere

[] Never

[] <1h/day

[] 1-4h/day

[] >4h/day

[] Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q031: Do those who visit your house smoke indoors?

[] Never

[] Rarely (less than 1 / month)

[] Sometimes (less than 1 / week)

[] 1 / week

[] 2-3 / week

[] 4-6 / week

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q161: How often do you consume alcoholic beverages?

[] (nearly) never

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

- 1 - 3 / month
- 1 - 3 / week
- 4 - 6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032: How often do you use the following cosmetic and hygiene products in the last month? For each product, please indicate if possible the commercial brand mostly used. **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1: Hair products **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.1: Spray, lacquer, gel/mousse **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.1.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.1.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.1.2: Shampoo **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.2.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.2.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.1.3: Conditioner **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.3.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.3.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.1.4: Moisturizer cream **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.4.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.4.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.1.5: Dye, colour rinse **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.5.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.5.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.1.6: Bleaching products **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.6.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.6.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.1.7: Perming products **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.7.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.7.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.1.8: Relaxer **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.8.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.8.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.1.9: Other products **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.9.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.9.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.9.3: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2: Cosmetics **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.2.1: Foundation (powder, liquid) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.2.1.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.1.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2.2: Make-up remover **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.2.2.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.2.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2.3: Lipbalm **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.2.3.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.3.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2.4: Lipstick **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.2.4.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.4.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2.5: Blusher **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.2.5.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.5.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2.6: Eye make-up (e.G.Mascare, eye shadow, eyeliner, mask, crayon) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.2.6.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.6.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2.7: Nail polish **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.2.7.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.7.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2.8: Nail polish remover **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.2.8.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.8.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2.9: Traditional cosmetics (kohl, surma, kajal, tiro, etc.) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.2.9.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.9.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2.10: Other products **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2.10.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.2.10.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2.10.3: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3: Bodycare **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.1: Perfume / eau de cologne **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.1.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.1.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.2: Body soap / shower gel **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.2.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.2.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.3: Hand lotion **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.3.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

Q032.3.3.2: Brand _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.3.4: Face cream (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.4.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.4.2: Brand _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.3.5: Face mask (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.5.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.5.2: Brand _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.3.6: Sun cream (sunscreen) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.6.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.6.2: Brand _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.3.7: Sun tan lotion (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.7.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.7.2: Brand _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.3.8: Anti-aging cream (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.8.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.8.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.9: Anti aging cream with sun protection factor **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.9.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.9.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.10: Deodorant **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.10.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.10.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.11: Shaving cream or aftershave lotion **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.11.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.11.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.12: Body oil or body lotion (cream, milk, ...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.12.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.12.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.13: Skin bleaching products **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.13.1: Frequency

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.13.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.14: Mouthwash **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.14.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.14.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.15: Dental floss **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.15.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.15.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.16: Other products **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.16.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.3.16.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.16.3: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q162: Do you pay attention to the composition of the personal care products you use or do you select products that are advertised as made without parabens, phthalates, sulphates...?

- No, never
- Yes, but rarely
- Yes, sometimes
- Yes, most of the time
- Yes, always

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

Q033: Did you use any of the following products in diy (do-it-yourself) activities or hobbies and/or were you exposed to any of these substances in the last 3 months? (please, do not count your professional activity)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.1: Paint, varnish, lacquer, dyes, inks, pigments

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.2: Solvents, degreasers, paint removers

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.3: Seals or fillers

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.4: Glues, adhesives

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.5: Wax (e.G., furniture, ski, horse saddles), epoxy resins

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.6: Leather cleaning products, leather preservatives

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.7: Lubricating oils (e.G., for tools, machines, bikes, music instruments, incl. Ptfе-products)

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.8: Cleaning chemicals

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.9: Computer and/or electronic device repair, welding/soldering

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.10: Teflon products (e.G. Kitchen appliances)

- Yes
- No

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.11: Water repellent clothing

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.12: Fireplace/combustion products (in/outdoors)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.13: Gardening products (fertilizers and pesticides)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q033.14: Sewage sludge (as fertilizer)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.15: Degrease tools, machines or electronics

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.16: Other products/activities

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.16.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q035: Have you done any body modifications (excluding medical interventions) in the last 5 years? If yes, specify the number, the size, the color and the age of each modification. **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q035.1: Piercings (including normal earrings)

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q035.1.1: Number _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q035.1.2.1: Piercing 1 _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q035.1.2.2: Piercing 2 _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q035.1.2.3: Piercing 3 _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q035.1.2.4: Piercing 4 _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q035.1.2.5: Piercing 5 _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q035.2: Tattoos (excluding cosmetic tattoos: microblading, lip blushing, and permanent eyeliner)

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q035.2.1: Number _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q035.2.2.1: Tattoo 1 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

- Q035.2.2.1.1: Size - length (in cm) _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q035.2.2.1.2: Size - width (in cm) _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q035.2.2.1.3: Color - red [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q035.2.2.1.4: Color - black [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q035.2.2.1.5: Color - other [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q035.2.2.1.6: Age of the tattoo
 - [] Less than 4 months
 - [] Between 4 and 12 months
 - [] More than a year

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

- Q035.2.2.2: Tattoo 2 (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.2.1: Size - length (in cm) _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.2.2: Size - width (in cm) _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.2.3: Color - red [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.2.4: Color - black [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.2.5: Color - other [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.2.6: Age of the tattoo
 - [] Less than 4 months
 - [] Between 4 and 12 months
 - [] More than a year

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

- Q035.2.2.3: Tattoo 3 (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.3.1: Size - length (in cm) _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.3.2: Size - width (in cm) _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.3.3: Color - red [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.3.4: Color - black [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.3.5: Color - other [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.3.6: Age of the tattoo
 - [] Less than 4 months
 - [] Between 4 and 12 months
 - [] More than a year

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

- Q035.2.2.4: Tattoo 4 (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.4.1: Size - length (in cm) _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.4.2: Size - width (in cm) _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.4.3: Color - red [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.4.4: Color - black [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.4.5: Color - other [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.4.6: Age of the tattoo
 - [] Less than 4 months
 - [] Between 4 and 12 months
 - [] More than a year

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

- Q035.2.2.5: Tattoo 5 (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.5.1: Size - length (in cm) _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.5.2: Size - width (in cm) _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.5.3: Color - red [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.5.4: Color - black [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.5.5: Color - other [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 - Q035.2.2.5.6: Age of the tattoo
 - [] Less than 4 months

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

Between 4 and 12 months

More than a year

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q035.3: Other modifications

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q035.3.1: Number _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q035.3.2: Age of other body modification _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q035.3.3: Specify other body modification _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q036: Do you have any artificial joints, pins, plates, metal suture material, or other types of metal objects in your body? (do not include piercings, crowns, dental braces or retainers, shrapnel, or bullets.)

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q037: How often do you usually wear metallic jewelry or watch bracelet, excluding gold, silver or platinum jewelry/bracelet?

Never/rarely

Sometimes (few times a month)

Always (almost daily)

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q038: Please, indicate how much time per day, on average, you have used electronic devices such as mobile phones, computers, tablets, gps... In the last month? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1: Weekdays **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.1: Portable devices (mobiles, tablets, laptops, gps...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.1.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.1.3: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.2: Desk devices (computer desk...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.2.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.2.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.2.3: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2: Weekends **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.1: Portable devices (mobiles, tablets, laptops, gps...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.1.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.1.3: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.2: Desk devices (computer desk...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.2.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.2.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.2.3: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q039: How long do you dedicate to sport and/or physical activities? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q039.1: Weekdays

No time

Less than 1 hour/day

1 hour/day (approx.)

2 hours/day (approx.)

3 hours/day (approx.)

4 hours/day (approx.)

> 4 hours/day

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q039.2: Weekends

No time

Less than 1 hour/day

1 hour/day (approx.)

2 hours/day (approx.)

3 hours/day (approx.)

4 hours/day (approx.)

> 4 hours/day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q040: Which of the following best describes your current physical exercise? Choose from the following options:

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q040.1: Light physical exercise for relaxation **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q040.1.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1 / week

A few times per week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q040.1.2: Duration

10-30 minutes

>= 30 minutes

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q040.2: Medium and intensive physical exercise **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q040.2.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1 / week

A few times per week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q040.2.2: Duration

10-30 minutes

>= 30 minutes

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q040.3: Intensive (vigorous) physical exercise (sweating/out of breath) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q040.3.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1 / week

A few times per week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q040.3.2: Duration

10-30 minutes

>= 30 minutes

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q041: How often (times per day) do you wash your hands?

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

- Twice a day or less
- 3-6 times a day
- More than 6 times a day
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q042: Do you have a habit of putting objects made of plastic (e.G. Pens, glasses or toys) in your mouth and chewing on them?

- No
- Yes

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q042.1: If yes, please specify the frequency

- Daily
- Several times per week
- Less often
- Don't know

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q043: Do you regularly wear plastic or rubber shoes such as e.G. Flip-flops, beach shoes, swimming shoes, crocs[®] or clogs without socks?

- Yes
- No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

I.05: Residential environment and home exposures

Q044: In which area is your home located?

- City centre
- Near city centre
- Suburb/metropolitan area
- Industrial
- Rural/village
- Other areas
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q044.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q046: Is your current home address and/or previous home address located near any of these facilities?

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q046.1: Agricultural fields (including vineyards and orchards)

- No
- Yes, < 150 m
- Yes, 150 - 500 m
- Yes, 500 - 1000 m
- Yes, > 1000 m
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q046.2: Greenhouses

- No
- Yes, < 150 m
- Yes, 150 - 500 m
- Yes, 500 - 1000 m

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Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q046.3: Natural spaces (parks, national parks...)

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q046.4: Firefighting facility, military base, airfield

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q046.5: Landfills, dump sites, sewage sludge treatment

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q046.6: Waste incinerator, power plant based coal, oil, gas or wood

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q046.7: Other sites where pesticides are used (e.G., golf yards, railway...)

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047: Is your current home address and/or previous home address located near any of these industries?

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047.1: Chemical industry (plastics, pesticides, tannery, pigments, cement, fertilizers,...)

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

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Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047.2: Paper or textile industry

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047.3: Metal industry (metals, no-ferro, steel, metal smeltery)

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047.4: Electronics (computer, electronics, photovoltaic devices, solar cells)

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047.5: A recycling plant, scrap yard, car repair plant

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047.6: A glass factory

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047.7: A site where medical equipment is produced

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047.8: Other industrial facilities

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

- No
- Yes, < 150 m
- Yes, 150 - 500 m
- Yes, 500 - 1000 m
- Yes, > 1000 m
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047.8.1: Specify facility _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q048: Does your house have garden and/or vegetable garden?

- Yes
- No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q048.1A: Has your garden been treated with pesticides in the last 12 months?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q048.1B: Has your vegetable garden been treated with pesticides in the last 12 months?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q050: Has your house (inside) or your workplace been treated with herbicides, fungicides and/or insecticides in the last 4 weeks? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q050.1: House

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q050.3: Workplace

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q051: Who applies pesticides in your home or garden?

- Yourself
- Another member of your household
- A professional
- Other

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q051.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q052: In the last 12 months, were insecticide/pesticide products used to control or repel pest problems in your garden? (e.G. Snails/slugs, weeds, mosses/lichens, other garden pests/insects).

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q053: What is the main water source for your home garden irrigation?

- Groundwater water (springs, wells)
- Private well
- Surface water (lake, river, streams, reservoir, ponds)

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

Rainwater

Others

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q053.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q054: Which of the following options best describes your home…?

Detached house

Semi-detached house

Townhouse

Flat/apartment

A farmhouse

Other (e.G. Caravan, mobile home)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q054.1: Flat/apartment: specify floor number _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q054.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q055: What materials are used for most of the floor coverings in your home? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1: Non-textile flooring **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.1: Wood-parquet **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.2: Wooden planks **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.3: Laminate **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.4: Pvc **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.5: Linoleum **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.6: Tiles (e.G. Stone, marble, terrazzo) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.7: Other non-textile material **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.7.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.2: Textile flooring **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.2.1: Synthetic fibre **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.2.2: Natural fibre **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.2.3: Natural or synthetic fibre with plastic backing **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.2.4: Other textile material **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.2.4.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.3: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q056: Are you in charge of the general cleaning of your home? (general cleaning includes vacuum cleaning, mopping - use of cleaners/chemicals, disinfectant products in water, sweeping, dusting)

No

Yes, entirely

Yes, partially

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q056.1: In that case specify the percentage you are in charge of _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q057: Do you use vacuum cleaner for general cleaning of your home? If yes, please, specify type and frequency of use

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q057.1: Type

Vacuum cleaner with air filter

Vacuum cleaner with water filter

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q057.2: Frequency

Less than 1 / week

1 / week

2 / week or more

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q160: Do you clean your home with water? If yes, please specify the frequency.

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q160.1: Frequency

Less than 1 / week

1 / week

2 / week or more

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058: In the last month, were any of the cleaning products listed below used in your home, at least once a week? If yes, please specify if the cleaning product generally used is a classical or eco-friendly product (product featuring an eco-label on the package) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q058.1: Cleaning products (e.G. For kitchen, bathroom, floor, windows)

No

Don't know

Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.1.1: Type of product

Classical

Eco-friendly

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.2: Floor wax

No

Don't know

Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.2.1: Type of product

Classical

Eco-friendly

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.3: Fabric softener

No

Don't know

Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.3.1: Type of product

Classical

Eco-friendly

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.4: Wood varnish

No

Don't know

Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.4.1: Type of product

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

- Classical
- Eco-friendly
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.5: Dry cleaning products (e.G. For cleaning upholstery, clothes, carpets)

- No
- Don't know
- Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.5.1: Type of product

- Classical
- Eco-friendly
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.6: Air freshener

- No
- Don't know
- Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.6.1: Type of product

- Classical
- Eco-friendly
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.7: Solvents (eg: cleaning solvents are acetone, toluene and trichloroethylene-tce. Common mild solvents include isopropyl alcohol, glycerin, and propylene glycol)

- No
- Don't know
- Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.7.1: Type of product

- Classical
- Eco-friendly
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.8: Spot remover products

- No
- Don't know
- Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.8.1: Type of product

- Classical
- Eco-friendly
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.9: Impregnation fluids (e.G. For upholstery, shoes)

- No
- Don't know
- Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.9.1: Type of product

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

- Classical
- Eco-friendly
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.10: Other cleaning products

- No
- Don't know
- Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.10.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q058.10.2: Type of product

- Classical
- Eco-friendly
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059: In the last 12 months, how much time on average did you spend in the following places (referred to weekdays and weekends) per season? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1: Fall **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1: Weekdays **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.1: Inside your home **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.1.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.1.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.2: Inside other houses **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.2.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.2.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.2.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. At workplace, shopping centre, sports club, cinema, restaurant...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.3.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.3.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.1.1.3.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.4: In your car **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.4.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.4.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.1.1.4.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.1.5.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.5.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.1.1.5.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus stops...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.6.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.6.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.1.1.6.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.1.7.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.7.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.1.1.7.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2: Weekends **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.1: Inside your home **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.1.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.1.2.1.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.2: Inside other houses **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.2.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.2.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.1.2.2.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. At workplace, shopping centre, sports club, cinema, restaurant...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.3.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.3.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.1.2.3.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.4: In your car **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.4.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.4.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.1.2.4.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.2.5.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.5.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.1.2.5.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus stops...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.6.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.6.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.1.2.6.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.2.7.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.7.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.1.2.7.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2: Winter **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1: Weekdays **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.1: Inside your home **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.1.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.1.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.2: Inside other houses **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.2.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.2.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.2.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. At workplace, shopping centre, sports club, cinema, restaurant...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.3.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.3.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.1.3.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.4: In your car **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.4.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.4.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

Q059.2.1.4.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.2.1.5.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.5.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.1.5.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus stops...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.6.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.6.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.1.6.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.2.1.7.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.7.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.1.7.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2: Weekends **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.1: Inside your home **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.1.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.2.1.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.2: Inside other houses **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.2.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.2.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.2.2.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. At workplace, shopping centre, sports club, cinema, restaurant...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.3.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.3.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.2.3.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.4: In your car **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.4.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.4.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.2.4.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.2.2.5.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.5.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.2.5.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus stops...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.6.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.6.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.2.6.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.2.2.7.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.7.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.2.7.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3: Spring **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1: Weekdays **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

- Q059.3.1.1: Inside your home **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.1.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.1.1.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.1.1.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q059.3.1.2: Inside other houses **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.1.2.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.1.2.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.1.2.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q059.3.1.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. At workplace, shopping centre, sports club, cinema, restaurant...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.1.3.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.1.3.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**
Q059.3.1.3.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q059.3.1.4: In your car **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.1.4.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.1.4.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**
Q059.3.1.4.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q059.3.1.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...)
(Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.3.1.5.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.1.5.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**
Q059.3.1.5.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q059.3.1.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus stops...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.1.6.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.1.6.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**
Q059.3.1.6.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q059.3.1.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...)
(Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.3.1.7.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.1.7.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**
Q059.3.1.7.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q059.3.2: Weekends **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.2.1: Inside your home **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.2.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.2.1.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**
Q059.3.2.1.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q059.3.2.2: Inside other houses **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.2.2.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.2.2.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**
Q059.3.2.2.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q059.3.2.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. At workplace, shopping centre, sports club, cinema, restaurant...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.2.3.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.2.3.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**
Q059.3.2.3.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q059.3.2.4: In your car **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.2.4.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q059.3.2.4.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**
Q059.3.2.4.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q059.3.2.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...)

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(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.5.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.5.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.3.2.5.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus stops...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.6.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.6.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.3.2.6.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.7.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.7.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.3.2.7.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4: Summer **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1: Weekdays **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.1: Inside your home **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.1.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.1.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.2: Inside other houses **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.2.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.2.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.2.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. At workplace, shopping centre, sports club, cinema, restaurant...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.3.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.3.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.4.1.3.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.4: In your car **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.4.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.4.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.4.1.4.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.5.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.5.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.4.1.5.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus stops...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.6.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.6.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.4.1.6.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.7.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.7.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.4.1.7.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2: Weekends **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.1: Inside your home **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

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Q059.4.2.1.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.4.2.1.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.2: Inside other houses (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.2.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.2.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.4.2.2.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. At workplace, shopping centre, sports club, cinema, restaurant...) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.3.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.3.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.4.2.3.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.4: In your car (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.4.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.4.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.4.2.4.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.5.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.5.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.4.2.5.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus stops...) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.6.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.6.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.4.2.6.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.7.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.7.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.4.2.7.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q060: Did you have any of these situations at home? (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q060.1: Breakage of a mercury thermometer

[] Yes

[] No

[] Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q060.1.1: Timing

[] Less than 6 months ago

[] Between 6 and 12 months ago

[] More than a year

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q060.2: Breakage of an energy-saving lamp

[] Yes

[] No

[] Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q060.2.1: Timing

[] Less than 6 months ago

[] Between 6 and 12 months ago

[] More than a year

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

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Q060.3: Which one(s) of these clean-up actions did you take? Please choose all that apply

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q060.3.1: Contained the spill by diking the mercury using rags

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q060.3.2: Picked up the pieces with rubber gloves on

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q060.3.3: Kept others away from the spill area to prevent the spread of contamination

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q060.3.4: Opened windows and doors in the area of the spill to provide ventilation during cleanup

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q060.3.5: Turned off heating, ventilating or air conditioning systems to prevent air circulation from the spill area to other parts of the house

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q060.3.6: Used a flashlight to determine if all the mercury was recovered

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q060.3.7: Other

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q060.3.7.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q061: Please complete the following information about redecorations and renovations made in your home.

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q061.1: Is your home currently being renovated? (major renovations: e.G. New walls, floor, windows···)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q061.2: Has your home been renovated in the last year? (major renovations: e.G. New walls, floor, windows···)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q061.3: Has your home been redecorated in the last year? (e.G. Painting, varnishing···)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q062: How is your house usually ventilated? For each option, please specify frequency of use (months/year in which

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

mechanical systems are used; hours/day for window ventilation by season) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q062.1: Mechanical ventilation system

- No
- Yes, always on
- Yes, sometimes switched off
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q062.2: Ventilation through opening windows or doors

- Yes
- No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q062.2.1: Frequency (autum-winter)

- Nearly never
- Less then daily
- Daily – for a short time
- Daily – for longer time (e.G. Half a day or whole day)
-

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q062.2.2: Frequency (spring-summer)

- Nearly never
- Less then daily
- Daily – for a short time
- Daily – for longer time (e.G. Half a day or whole day)
-

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q062.3: Does you house have ventilation grilles in windows/doors or walls?

- No
- Yes, but they are sometimes closed
- Yes, they are always open
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q063: Do you have any pets at home or did you have any pets at home in the last 12 months? If so, specify type and number **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q063.1: No animal **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q063.2: Dog

- Yes
- No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q063.2.1: Number _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q063.3: Cat

- Yes
- No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q063.3.1: Number _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q063.4: Bird

- Yes
- No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q063.4.1: Number _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q063.5: Other animal

- Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q063.5.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q063.5.1.1: Number _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q063.5.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q063.5.2.1: Number _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

I.06: Occupational exposures

Q064: What is your occupation/profession? _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q066: Please, describe your current job _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q067: How long have you been doing this job? Specify years or months, if less than one year **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q067.1: Years _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q067.2: Months _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068: Do you come into contact with the following substances on your current job? Note: contact can occur via the skin and/or by inhalation. **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q068.1: Combustion products, including gasoline/diesel exhausts, ash or soot

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q068.1.1: Specify: (e.G. Aluminium production, chimney sweeping, coking plants, firefighting/ fire practice/ fire prevention training, foundry industry, garage work, heating/ thermal power plants, metallurgic industry, mining, vehicle inspection, vehicle depots, waste incineration) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q068.2: Metals (eg. Mercury, lead, cadmium, chromium, others)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q068.2.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q068.3: Paints/ coatings including varnishes

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q068.3.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q068.4: Printing inks

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q068.4.1: Specify: (e.G. Ink production, printing industry, other job, which?) _____

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q068.5: Solvents

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.5.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

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Q068.6: Plasticisers and plastics

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q068.6.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.7: Pesticides, biocides or disinfection products (herbicides, fungicides, insecticides or bactericides)

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q068.7.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.8: Cosmetics or hair treatment products (hair dyes etc.)

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q068.8.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q068.9: Polymers production (monomers)

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q068.9.1: Specify: plastic products production _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q068.10: Flame retardants

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.10.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.11: Photoresist/antireflective coatings

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.11.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.12: Cytotoxic drugs (e.G. Cyclophosphamide, doxorubicine, methotrexate...)

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.12.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.13: Anaesthetic gases (e.G. desflurane, isoflurane, nitrous oxide...)

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.13.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.14: Disinfection and cleaning products (e.G. Ethanol, isopropylalcohol...)

- Yes
- No

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Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.14.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.15: E-waste (electric or electronic devices)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.15.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.16: Plastic waste

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.16.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.17: Other hazardous materials, hazardous waste or other chemicals

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.17.1: Specify: (e.G. Contaminated soil renovation) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.18: Other compounds

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.18.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q069: In the working environment in which you perform working tasks/activities are there technical risk management measures (e.G. Collective protective measures such as local exhaust ventilation, enclosing of the exposure source...) available?

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q069.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070: Please list each of the previous jobs where you have worked, over / back to the past 10 years: for each job, specify the substance which you came in contact with. **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.1: Job no.1 **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.1.1: Sector of industry/ workplace _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.1.2: Job description _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.1.3: Job duration **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.1.3.1: Years _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.1.3.2: Months _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.1.4: Exposure to substances (same as q068) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.2: Job no.2 **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.2.1: Sector of industry/ workplace _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.2.2: Job description _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.2.3: Job duration **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.2.3.1: Years _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.2.3.2: Months _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.2.4: Exposure to substances (same as q068) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

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Q070.3: Job no.3 **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.3.1: Sector of industry/ workplace _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.3.2: Job description _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.3.3: Job duration **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.3.3.1: Years _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.3.3.2: Months _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.3.4: Exposure to substances (same as q068) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.4: Job no.4 **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.4.1: Sector of industry/ workplace _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.4.2: Job description _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.4.3: Job duration **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.4.3.1: Years _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.4.3.2: Months _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.4.4: Exposure to substances (same as q068) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.5: Job no.5 **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.5.1: Sector of industry/ workplace _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.5.2: Job description _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.5.3: Job duration **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.5.3.1: Years _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.5.3.2: Months _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.5.4: Exposure to substances (same as q068) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.6: Job no.6 **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.6.1: Sector of industry/ workplace _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.6.2: Job description _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.6.3: Job duration **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.6.3.1: Years _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.6.3.2: Months _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.6.4: Exposure to substances (same as q068) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.7: Job no.7 **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.7.1: Sector of industry/ workplace _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.7.2: Job description _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.7.3: Job duration **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.7.3.1: Years _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.7.3.2: Months _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q070.7.4: Exposure to substances (same as q068) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q071: From the following list of working tasks/activities, please, indicate if you perform them in carrying out your job, the duration and frequency in a work shift, the use of ppe and the availability of collective protective measures

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.1: Application of herbicides

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.1.1: Duration (hours/day)

Less than 0,5 (hours/day)

0,5-2 (hours/day)

2-4 (hours/day)

4-8 (hours/day)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.1.2: Frequency (days/week)

Less than 1 (day/week)

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- 1 (day/week)
- 2-3 (days/week)
- 4-5 (days/week)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.1.3: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.1.3.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q071.1.4: Availability of collective protective measures

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.1.4.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q071.2: Application of insecticides

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.2.1: Duration (hours/day)

- Less than 0,5 (hours/day)
- 0,5-2 (hours/day)
- 2-4 (hours/day)
- 4-8 (hours/day)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.2.2: Frequency (days/week)

- Less than 1 (day/week)
- 1 (day/week)
- 2-3 (days/week)
- 4-5 (days/week)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.2.3: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.2.3.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q071.2.4: Availability of collective protective measures

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.2.4.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q071.3: Application of fungicides

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.3.1: Duration (hours/day)

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Less than 0,5 (hours/day)

0,5-2 (hours/day)

2-4 (hours/day)

4-8 (hours/day)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.3.2: Frequency (days/week)

Less than 1 (day/week)

1 (day/week)

2-3 (days/week)

4-5 (days/week)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.3.3: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.3.3.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q071.3.4: Availability of collective protective measures

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.3.4.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q071.4: Production/formulation/sale of herbicides

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.4.1: Duration (hours/day)

Less than 0,5 (hours/day)

0,5-2 (hours/day)

2-4 (hours/day)

4-8 (hours/day)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.4.2: Frequency (days/week)

Less than 1 (day/week)

1 (day/week)

2-3 (days/week)

4-5 (days/week)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.4.3: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.4.3.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q071.4.4: Availability of collective protective measures

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

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Q071.4.4.1: Please specify _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.5: Production/formulation/sale of insecticides

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.5.1: Duration (hours/day)

Less than 0,5 (hours/day)

0,5-2 (hours/day)

2-4 (hours/day)

4-8 (hours/day)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.5.2: Frequency (days/week)

Less than 1 (day/week)

1 (day/week)

2-3 (days/week)

4-5 (days/week)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.5.3: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.5.3.1: Please specify _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.5.4: Availability of collective protective measures

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.5.4.1: Please specify _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.6: Production/formulation/sale of fungicides

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.6.1: Duration (hours/day)

Less than 0,5 (hours/day)

0,5-2 (hours/day)

2-4 (hours/day)

4-8 (hours/day)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.6.2: Frequency (days/week)

Less than 1 (day/week)

1 (day/week)

2-3 (days/week)

4-5 (days/week)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.6.3: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

No

Yes

Don't know

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.6.3.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q071.6.4: Availability of collective protective measures

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.6.4.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q071.7: Agricultural labour (outdoors)

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.7.1: Duration (hours/day)

- Less than 0,5 (hours/day)
- 0,5-2 (hours/day)
- 2-4 (hours/day)
- 4-8 (hours/day)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.7.2: Frequency (days/week)

- Less than 1 (day/week)
- 1 (day/week)
- 2-3 (days/week)
- 4-5 (days/week)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.7.3: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.7.3.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q071.7.4: Availability of collective protective measures

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.7.4.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q071.8: Agricultural labour (greenhouses)

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.8.1: Duration (hours/day)

- Less than 0,5 (hours/day)
- 0,5-2 (hours/day)
- 2-4 (hours/day)
- 4-8 (hours/day)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.8.2: Frequency (days/week)

- Less than 1 (day/week)
- 1 (day/week)

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

2-3 (days/week)

4-5 (days/week)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.8.3: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.8.3.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q071.8.4: Availability of collective protective measures

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.8.4.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q071.9: Working in a fruit/vegetable warehouse

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.9.1: Duration (hours/day)

Less than 0,5 (hours/day)

0,5-2 (hours/day)

2-4 (hours/day)

4-8 (hours/day)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.9.2: Frequency (days/week)

Less than 1 (day/week)

1 (day/week)

2-3 (days/week)

4-5 (days/week)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.9.3: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.9.3.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q071.9.4: Availability of collective protective measures

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.9.4.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q071.10: Working in extermination, disinfection or/and pest control

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.10.1: Duration (hours/day)

Less than 0,5 (hours/day)

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

0,5-2 (hours/day)

2-4 (hours/day)

4-8 (hours/day)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.10.2: Frequency (days/week)

Less than 1 (day/week)

1 (day/week)

2-3 (days/week)

4-5 (days/week)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.10.3: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.10.3.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q071.10.4: Availability of collective protective measures

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.10.4.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q071.11: Gardening

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.11.1: Duration (hours/day)

Less than 0,5 (hours/day)

0,5-2 (hours/day)

2-4 (hours/day)

4-8 (hours/day)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.11.2: Frequency (days/week)

Less than 1 (day/week)

1 (day/week)

2-3 (days/week)

4-5 (days/week)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.11.3: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.11.3.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q071.11.4: Availability of collective protective measures

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.11.4.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

Q071.12: Other activities involving using or handling pesticides

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.12.1: Duration (hours/day)

Less than 0,5 (hours/day)

0,5-2 (hours/day)

2-4 (hours/day)

4-8 (hours/day)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.12.2: Frequency (days/week)

Less than 1 (day/week)

1 (day/week)

2-3 (days/week)

4-5 (days/week)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.12.3: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.12.3.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q071.12.4: Availability of collective protective measures

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q071.12.4.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q072: In your previous jobs, have you performed any of the following working tasks/activities (if yes, please, indicate the total period of exposure, the use of ppe (personal protective equipment) and the availability of collective protective measures)? **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q072.1: Application of herbicides

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.1.1: Period of exposure (years)

Less than 1 year

1-2 years

2-5 years

5-10 years

10-15 years

15-20 years

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.1.2: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.1.2.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

Q072.1.3: Availability of collective protective measures

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.1.3.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q072.2: Application of insecticides

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.2.1: Period of exposure (years)

- Less than 1 year
- 1-2 years
- 2-5 years
- 5-10 years
- 10-15 years
- 15-20 years

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.2.2: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.2.2.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q072.2.3: Availability of collective protective measures

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.2.3.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q072.3: Application of fungicides

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.3.1: Period of exposure (years)

- Less than 1 year
- 1-2 years
- 2-5 years
- 5-10 years
- 10-15 years
- 15-20 years

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.3.2: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.3.2.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q072.3.3: Availability of collective protective measures

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.3.3.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q072.4: Production or formulation of herbicides

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.4.1: Period of exposure (years)

- Less than 1 year
- 1-2 years
- 2-5 years
- 5-10 years
- 10-15 years
- 15-20 years

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.4.2: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.4.2.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q072.4.3: Availability of collective protective measures

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.4.3.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q072.5: Production or formulation of insecticides

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.5.1: Period of exposure (years)

- Less than 1 year
- 1-2 years
- 2-5 years
- 5-10 years
- 10-15 years
- 15-20 years

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.5.2: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.5.2.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q072.5.3: Availability of collective protective measures

- No

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.5.3.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q072.6: Production or formulation of fungicides

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.6.1: Period of exposure (years)

Less than 1 year

1-2 years

2-5 years

5-10 years

10-15 years

15-20 years

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.6.2: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.6.2.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q072.6.3: Availability of collective protective measures

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.6.3.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q072.7: Agricultural labour (outdoors)

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.7.1: Period of exposure (years)

Less than 1 year

1-2 years

2-5 years

5-10 years

10-15 years

15-20 years

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.7.2: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.7.2.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q072.7.3: Availability of collective protective measures

No

Yes

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.7.3.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q072.8: Agricultural labour (greenhouses)

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.8.1: Period of exposure (years)

Less than 1 year

1-2 years

2-5 years

5-10 years

10-15 years

15-20 years

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.8.2: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.8.2.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q072.8.3: Availability of collective protective measures

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.8.3.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q072.9: Working in a fruit/vegetable warehouse

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.9.1: Period of exposure (years)

Less than 1 year

1-2 years

2-5 years

5-10 years

10-15 years

15-20 years

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.9.2: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.9.2.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q072.9.3: Availability of collective protective measures

No

Yes

Don't know

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.9.3.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q072.10: Working in extermination, disinfection or/and pest control

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.10.1: Period of exposure (years)

Less than 1 year

1-2 years

2-5 years

5-10 years

10-15 years

15-20 years

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.10.2: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.10.2.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q072.10.3: Availability of collective protective measures

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.10.3.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q072.11: Gardening

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.11.1: Period of exposure (years)

Less than 1 year

1-2 years

2-5 years

5-10 years

10-15 years

15-20 years

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.11.2: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.11.2.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q072.11.3: Availability of collective protective measures

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

Q072.11.3.1: Please specify _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.12: Other activities involving using or handling pesticides

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.12.1: Period of exposure (years)

Less than 1 year

1-2 years

2-5 years

5-10 years

10-15 years

15-20 years

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.12.2: Use of ppe (personal protective equipment)

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.12.2.1: Please specify _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.12.3: Availability of collective protective measures

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q072.12.3.1: Please specify _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

I.07: Health status

Q073: How tall are you (in cm)? _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q074: How much do you weight (in kg)? _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q075: What is your current waist circumference? _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077: Do you have or ever had amalgam fillings (grey color) and/or dental sealant in your teeth?

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.1: In how many teeth? (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.1.1: Amalgam fillings (grey color) _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.1.2: Dental sealant (white color) _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.1.3: Don't know (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.2: When was the amalgam filling placed last time? (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.2.1: Days _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.2.2: Months _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.2.3: Years _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.2.4: Don't know (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.3: When was the dental sealant (white color) placed last time? (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.3.1: Days _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.3.2: Months _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

Q077.3.3: Years _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.3.4: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.4: When was the amalgam filling removed from your teeth last time? (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.4.1: Days _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.4.2: Months _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.4.3: Years _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.4.4: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.5: When was the dental sealant removed from your teeth last time? (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.5.1: Days _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.5.2: Months _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.5.3: Years _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q077.5.4: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q078: Do you use glasses and/or contact eye lenses?

[] Yes, glasses

[] Yes, contact lenses

[] Yes, both

[] No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079: Have you or any of your biological family members (father, mother, siblings, grand-mother, grand-father...) been diagnosed by a medical doctor with any of the following diseases or conditions? If yes, has it occurred within the last 12 months, please specify how old was the participant when this was first diagnosed. (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.1: Asthma (allergic asthma included) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.1.1: You

[] Never

[] Yes, in the past 12 months

[] Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.1.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.1.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.2: Chronic bronchitis, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (copd), emphysema

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.2.1: You

[] Never

[] Yes, in the past 12 months

[] Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.2.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.2.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.3: Myocardial infarction (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.3.1: You

[] Never

[] Yes, in the past 12 months

[] Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.3.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.3.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.4: Coronary heart disease (angina pectoris) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.4.1: You

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.4.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.4.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.5: High blood pressure (hypertension) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.5.1: You
- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.5.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.5.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.6: Elevated blood cholesterol **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.6.1: You
- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.6.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.6.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.7: Stroke (cerebral haemorrhage, cerebral thrombosis) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.7.1: You
- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.7.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.7.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.8: Rheumatoid arthritis (inflammation of the joints) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.8.1: You
- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.8.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.8.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.9: Osteoarthritis (arthrosis, joint degeneration) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.9.1: You
- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.9.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

Q079.1.9.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.10: Osteoporosis (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.10.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.10.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.10.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.11: Low back disorder or other chronic back defect (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.11.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.11.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.11.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.12: Neck disorder or other chronic neck defect (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.12.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.12.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.12.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.13: Type 1 diabetes (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.13.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.13.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.13.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.14: Type 2 diabetes (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.14.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.14.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.14.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.15: Thyroid disease (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.15.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

ANNEX 3.3 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ADULTS

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.15.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.15.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.16: Allergy (any other type than the following: allergic rhinitis, allergic conjunctivitis, allergic dermatitis) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.16.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.16.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.16.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.17: Allergic rhinitis (nasal itching, sneezing, runny nose, or nasal blockage) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.17.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.17.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.17.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.18: Allergic conjunctivitis **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.18.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.18.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.18.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.19: Allergic dermatitis **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.19.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.19.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.19.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.20: Anaphylaxis (symptoms: airway constriction that makes it difficult to breath, shock with severe drop of blood pressure, rapid pulse, dizziness, or lightheadedness) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.20.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.20.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

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Q079.1.20.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.21: Stomach ulcer (gastric or duodenal ulcer) (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.21.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.21.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.21.2: Family member _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.22: cirrhosis or fibrosis of the liver/liver disease or dysfunction (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.22.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.22.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.22.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.23: kidney disease or dysfunction (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.23.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.23.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.23.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.24: cancer (malignant tumour, also including leukaemia and lymphoma) (see next question to specify kind of cancer) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.24.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.24.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.24.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.25: Severe headache such as migraine (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.25.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.25.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.25.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.26: urinary incontinence, problems in controlling the bladder or other gallbladder problems (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.26.1: You

Never

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- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.26.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.26.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.27: chronic anxiety **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 - Q079.1.27.1: You
 - Never
 - Yes, in the past 12 months
 - Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.27.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.27.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.28: Chronic depression **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 - Q079.1.28.1: You
 - Never
 - Yes, in the past 12 months
 - Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.28.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.28.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.29: Other mental health problems **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 - Q079.1.29.1: You
 - Never
 - Yes, in the past 12 months
 - Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.29.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.29.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.30: spinal cord disorders **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 - Q079.1.30.1: You
 - Never
 - Yes, in the past 12 months
 - Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.30.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.30.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.31: attention deficit disorders (add, adhd) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 - Q079.1.31.1: You
 - Never
 - Yes, in the past 12 months
 - Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.31.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.31.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

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Q079.1.32: Autism or autism spectrum dysfunction **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.32.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.32.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.32.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.33: asperger syndrome **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.33.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.33.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.33.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.34: Down syndrome or other chromosomal disorder **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.34.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.34.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.34.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.35: neurodegenerative diseases (parkinson's disease, alzheimer's disease, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis and etc.) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.35.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.35.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.35.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.36: Learning disability (dyslexia and etc.) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.36.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.36.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.36.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.37: Neurological disorders **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.37.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

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3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.37.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.37.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.38: Permanent injury or defect caused by an accident **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.38.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.38.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.38.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.39: (for women only) gynaecological diseases **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.39.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.39.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.39.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.40: (for men only) prostate diseases **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.40.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.40.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.40.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.41: Other diseases or conditions. **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.41.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.41.1.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.41.1.2: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q079.1.41.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.41.2.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.2: If you answered “yes” for cancer, please specify what kind of cancer. Choose from the following options: **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.2.1: Bladder **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.2.2: Blood **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.2.3: Bone **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.2.4: Breast **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.2.5: Cervix(cervical) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.2.6: Colon **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.2.7: Esophagus (esophageal) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

- Q079.2.8: Brain [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.9: Gallbladder [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.10: Kidney [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.11: Larynx/windpipe [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.12: Leukaemia [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.13: Liver [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.14: Lung [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.15: Lymphoma/hodgkin's disease [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.16: Melanoma [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.17: Mouth/tongue/lip [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.18: Nervous system [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.19: Ovary(ovarian) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.20: Pancreas(pancreatic) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.21: Prostate [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.22: Rectum (rectal) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.23: Skin(non-melanoma) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.24: Skin (don't know what kind) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.25: Soft tissue (muscle or fat) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.26: Stomach [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.27: Testis (testicular) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.28: Thyroid [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.29: Uterus (uterine) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.30: Other [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.30.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.31: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080: During the past two weeks, have you used any medicines or homeopathic medicines?

- [] Yes
 [] No
 [] Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1: If yes, please indicate the commercial name(s) of the medicine, for which condition, the indication, as well as the strength of the drug, dose and frequency of use. **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

- Q080.2.1.1: Medicine 1 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.1.1: Commercial name _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.1.2: Condition _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.1.3: Indication _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.1.4: Dose _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.1.5: Frequency of use _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.1.6: Starting date **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.1.7: Ending date **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.2: Medicine 2 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.2.1: Commercial name _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.2.2: Condition _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.2.3: Indication _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.2.4: Dose _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.2.5: Frequency of use _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.1.6: Starting date **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.1.7: Ending date **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.3: Medicine 3 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.3.1: Commercial name _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.3.2: Condition _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.3.3: Indication _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.3.4: Dose _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.3.5: Frequency of use _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.1.6: Starting date (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.1.7: Ending date (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.4: Medicine 4 (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.4.1: Commercial name _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.4.2: Condition _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.4.3: Indication _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.4.4: Dose _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.4.5: Frequency of use _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.1.6: Starting date (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.1.7: Ending date (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q081: Which of the following options best describes your menstrual cycle? I have (had) menstrual periods

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q081.1: What age did you get your period for the first time? Age at menarche _____

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q083: Are you currently on your period

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q083.1: My period stopped permanently: menopause **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q083.1.1: Specify type of menopause

Natural

Hormone therapy

Surgical

Don't know

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q084: Have you ever been pregnant? (including current pregnancy, live births, miscarriages, stillbirths, tubal pregnancies or abortions)

Yes

No

Do not wish to answer

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q084.1: Specify number _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q085: Please, complete the following information for each of your pregnancies **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q085.1: Pregnancy no.1 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q085.1.1: Miscarriages

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q085.1.2: Abortion

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q085.1.3: Live birth

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

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Q085.1.4: Polyembryotic

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q085.1.5: Birth defects

Yes

No

Do not wish to answer

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q085.2: Pregnancy no.2 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q085.2.1: Miscarriages

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q085.2.2: Abortion

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q085.2.3: Live birth

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q085.2.4: Polyembryotic

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q085.2.5: Birth defects

Yes

No

Do not wish to answer

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q085.3: Pregnancy no.3 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q085.3.1: Miscarriages

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q085.3.2: Abortion

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q085.3.3: Live birth

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q085.3.4: Polyembryotic

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q085.3.5: Birth defects

Yes

No

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Do not wish to answer

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q085.4: Pregnancy no.4 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q085.4.1: Miscarriages

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q085.4.2: Abortion

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q085.4.3: Live birth

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q085.4.4: Polyembryotic

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q085.4.5: Birth defects

Yes

No

Do not wish to answer

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q085.5: Pregnancy no.5 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q085.5.1: Miscarriages

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q085.5.2: Abortion

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q085.5.3: Live birth

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q085.5.4: Polyembryotic

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q085.5.5: Birth defects

Yes

No

Do not wish to answer

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q085.6: Pregnancy no.6 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q085.6.1: Miscarriages

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

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Q085.6.2: Abortion

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q085.6.3: Live birth

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q085.6.4: Polyembryotic

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q085.6.5: Birth defects

Yes

No

Do not wish to answer

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q086: Have you ever been diagnosed with preeclampsia for any of your pregnancies?

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q087: Are you breast feeding or have breastfed? If so, please indicate the length of breastfeeding. For women with several children, specify total months of breastfeeding. (please note that breast feeding includes pumping of breast milk)

Yes, i am breastfeeding

Yes, i had breast-fed

Yes, both

No

Do not wish to answer

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q087.1: Yes, i am breastfeeding **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q087.1.1: Specify length: weeks (if less than 1 month) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q087.1.2: Specify length: months _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q087.2: Yes, i had breast-fed **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q087.2.1: Specify length: weeks (if less than 1 month) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q087.2.2: Specify length: months _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q087.3: Yes, both **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q087.3.1: Specify length: weeks (if less than 1 month) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q087.3.2: Specify length: months _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q088: Are you currently pregnant?

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q088.1: If yes, how long have you had unprotected sexual intercourse before becoming pregnant? (time to pregnancy ttp is defined as the number of months of unprotected intercourse that elapse before conception occurs) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q089: Have there been time periods when you have attempted to have a child but have not succeeded or it took over 12 months to succeed?

I don't know, because we or i have never tried to have a baby

No

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Yes

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q089.1: Most recently, how many years ago? _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q090: Have you ever been examined or been treated for infertility?

Yes

No

Do not wish to answer

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q090.1: What was the reason for your infertility?

Damage of the fallopian tube (e.G. Obstructions)

Disturbance of the ovulation

Endometriosis

Reasons related to the male partner

(e.G. Weak sperm movement or slow sperm count)

Reason is unclear

Other reason

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q090.1.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q091: Have there been time periods when you have attempted to have a child but have not succeeded or it took over 12 months to succeed?

I don't know, because we or i have never tried to have a baby

No

Yes

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q091.1: Most recently, how many years ago? _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q092: Have you ever been examined or been treated for infertility?

Yes

No

Do not wish to answer

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q092.1: What was the reason for your infertility?

Weak sperm movement

Low sperm count

Abnormal sperm shape

Reasons related to the female partner

(e.G. Damage of the fallopian tube, disturbance of the ovulation, endometriosis)

Reason is unclear

Other

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q092.1.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**